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INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

went extinct in the F0, springtails in the following generations were exposed to FBSA concentrations up to 1.06 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil. An EC50 of 1.10 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil was obtained for reproduction in the F1 generation, but no significant adverse effect was observed on any endpoint in any other generation. It was speculated that *F. candida* could biotransform the FBSA into PFBS, but a potential biotransformation capacity threshold lies between 1.06 and 9.64 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil. It is concluded that PFBS is not very toxic to *F. candida*, but FBSA is more than 100 times more toxic, with concentration-response relationships turning into an all-or-nothing effect at a specific threshold. The comparatively high ecotoxicity of the barely tested precursor FBSA challenges the environmental risk assessment of PFAS, which is currently based on a limited number of compounds. This research was supported by the Open Technology Programme of the Dutch Research Council (NWO) [grant number 18725]

1.01.P-Tu004 Neurobehavioral Impairments in the Sea Bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) Chronically Exposed to Cadmium and Ciprofloxacin Contaminated Diets

Juliette Bedrossiantz¹, Janan Gawra¹, Nerea Sanchis², Paula Medina², Demetrio Raldua¹, Joana Luisa Pereira³, Mercedes Blazquez² and Laia Navarro-Martin¹, (1)Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research, Spain, (2)Institute of Marine Sciences (ICM-CSIC), Spain, (3) University of Aveiro, Portugal

Environmental contamination by heavy metals and pharmaceuticals poses significant risks to marine ecosystems, as they can alter the behavior and survival of aquatic organisms. Cadmium (Cd) is a heavy metal recognized for its high neurotoxicity even at low concentrations such as those found in natural ecosystems. Ciprofloxacin (CIP) is a fluoroquinolone antibiotic that is increasingly detected in aquatic environments and could alter microbial communities, affecting the gut health of fish and interfering with neuronal functions through the microbiota-gut-brain axis. This study focuses on understanding the sublethal effects of these two environmental contaminants in the juvenile model of European sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax* after 21 days of dietary exposure. For each compound, two concentrations belonging to the environmental ranges (Cd: 10 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg; CIP: 1 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg) were chosen. After exposure, we evaluated *D. labrax* behavior with a battery of behavioral tests including the social preference test (SPT), the shoaling test (ST), the light-dark test (LDT) and the group exploratory test (ET). Exposure to Cd and CIP caused significant dose-dependent behavioral alterations. In the SPT, fish exposed to higher concentrations showed less social interaction, with a reduction in the distance travelled in the conspecific compartment. In the ST, a tendency towards cohesion was observed, significant in animals exposed to the highest concentration of Cd. In the LDT, we found a pattern of anxiogenic response concomitant with depression as indicated by the prolonged time in the illuminated zone. The time in the illuminated zone increased significantly when this test was repeated as a group in the ET. Finally, we found in all cases a significant decrease in basal locomotor activity and an increase in freezing episodes.

Reduced swimming activity, changes in social behavior and alterations in exploratory and decision-making behaviors indicate that dietary exposure to Cd and CIP, even at environmentally relevant concentrations, could affect the survival and ecological fitness of the species. These results underscore the need to add sublethal endpoints in toxicological monitoring studies to preserve marine environments. Further analysis will evaluate transcriptomic and epigenetic responses and link effects at the molecular level to behavioural impairment caused by exposures to Cd and CIP.

1.01.P-Tu005 Effects of Cadmium in *Acartia tonsa*: Epigenetic and phenotypic responses

Ana Beatriz Rodrigues¹, Ilias Semmouri², Albano Pinto¹, Ines PE Macario¹, Sergio Marques¹, Joana Lourenco¹, Ines Domingues¹, Joana Luisa Pereira¹ and Jana Asselman², (1)University of Aveiro, Portugal, (2)University of Ghent, Belgium

Increasing anthropogenic activities are significantly impacting aquatic ecosystems, leading to contamination and potential deleterious effects in organisms. Cadmium, a trace metal with no essential biological role known, is particularly harmful due to its high toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulation potential. Herein, we assessed the potential link between DNA methylation and different phenotypic endpoints as a response to short-term (48 h) cadmium exposure (238.8 µg/L, corresponding to the pre-estimated immobilization EC20) of the marine copepod *Acartia tonsa*, a zooplanktonic marine species with important ecological role and established as a model organism in ecotoxicology. Epigenetic changes were assessed through quantification of global 5-mC DNA methylation. Biomarkers of oxidative stress and damage were assessed by measuring glutathione S-transferases (GSTs) activity and the extent of lipid peroxidation, through the TBARS method, while genotoxicity was analyzed by inspecting DNA damage using the comet assay. Additionally, post-exposure swimming behavior of *A. tonsa* was analyzed by automated video-tracking. Global 5-mC DNA methylation levels slightly decreased among exposed copepods, suggesting a global hypomethylation trend. Phenotypically, this corresponded to a significant

increase in genotoxicity, a significant increase in GST activity accompanied by an increase in oxidative damage. Regarding copepods behavior, including swimming distance and swimming speed, an impairment can be noticed, but only at concentrations higher than the EC20, thus higher than those provoking recognizable effects in the other tested biomarkers. This approach supports a better understanding of cadmium's effects on marine copepods, by following adverse outcomes initiated with epigenetic mechanisms at the molecular, biochemical and individual level. As the present work becomes complete with currently ongoing whole epigenome and whole transcriptome analysis, molecular basis for adverse outcome pathways for toxicity caused by stressors such as cadmium in copepods will certainly be characterized, which should clarify further the interconnection of the responses found in the present work. Project EPIBOOST, funded by the EU through Grant 101078991; CESAM by FCT/MCTES (UIDP/50017/2020 + UIDB/50017/2020 + LA/P/0094/2020); AP by FCT - 2022.10817.BD. JL by national funds (OE), through FCT - framework contract foreseen in Decree- Law 57/2016, changed by Law 57/2017.

1.01.P-Tu006 DNA Methylation and Ocean Acidification: Insights from *Patella caerulea* at the Natural CO₂ Vent Systems of Ischia Island

*Silvia Giorgia Signorini*¹, *Camilla Della Torre*¹, *Marco Giulio*², *Marco Munari*³, *Fabio Crocetta*⁴, *Lara Nigro*⁵, *Ilaria D'Aniello*³ and *Alexandra Anh-Thu Weber*², (1)University of Milan; Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Italy, (2)Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag), Switzerland, (3)Stazione Idrobiologica Umberto d Ancona, University of Padova, Italy, (4)Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Italy, (5)University of Milan, Italy

Ocean acidification (OA) represents one of the major threats to marine biota, especially to calcifying organisms. Within this context, CO₂ vent systems, which are naturally acidified sites by volcanic CO₂ emitted from the seafloor, represent a perfect window into the future, where it is possible to investigate the effects of OA on marine organisms exposed to this environmental disturbance for their entire life cycle, allowing to take into consideration any potential acclimation and/or adaptation strategies. In particular, there is evidence that epigenetic modifications, such as DNA methylation, might play a fundamental role in organisms adaptation to stress, since they can contribute to physiological plasticity but they could also promote genetic adaptation. In view of this, DNA methylation was investigated in populations of the calcifying species *Patella caerulea* collected in both winter and summer seasons from the natural pH gradient of the Castello Aragonese vent systems (Ischia Island) (N1: ambient pH = 8.1; N2: intermediate pH = 7.7; N3: very low pH = <7.4) and from the ambient pH site San Pietro (SP: ambient pH = 8.1). Genomic DNA was extracted from foot tissue of 15 individuals per site, and whole genome enzymatic methyl-seq (EMseq) libraries were constructed and sequenced on the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 sequencer. Reads were aligned to the *P. caerulea* reference genome and methylation at CpG sites was extracted using MethylKit R package. Pair-wise comparisons carried out inside the Castello Aragonese vent systems revealed that few sites were differentially methylated, indicating no difference in DNA methylation among ambient and acidified sites. Furthermore, the analysis related to seasonality (winter vs summer) within site, showed that 184 CpGs were differentially methylated in San Pietro, while inside the vent systems, the number of differentially methylated cytosines drastically reduced to 11 in N1, and to 0 in both the acidified sites N2 and N3. Previous research has highlighted that higher epigenetic plasticity might induce a greater metabolic cost to the organism. Considering that, these results could suggest that limpets living in the acidified sites of the vent may not be able to modulate DNA methylation in response to OA. Alternatively, it could be that further mechanisms are involved, such as differences in gene expression, or other epigenetic mechanisms (histone modifications, chromatin accessibility).

1.01.P-Tu007 Investigating the Effects of Glyphosate Exposure on Survival, Reproduction, and Development in *Drosophila melanogaster*

Tolulope Ajayi and *Caitriona Collins*, *Technological University of the Shannon Midlands: Midwest (Athlone), Ireland*

The need for global food security has led to a reliance on chemical pesticides and their heavy use has led to severe declines in insect populations over the last 30-years. Biodiversity loss disrupts delicate ecosystems and has far-reaching consequences. Glyphosate, the active compound in widely used herbicides Gallup and Roundup, is effective, but persists in soil and water, posing acute and chronic exposure risks to humans and non-target species. Sublethal concentrations of glyphosate have been shown to have negative effects on insect development and fertility, sublethal doses reduce egg viability, alter spermatogenesis and disrupt embryonic development. This study aims to investigate the molecular mechanisms of glyphosate-based herbicide (GBH) toxicity on insect fertility and development using the fruit fly, *Drosophila melanogaster* as a model. Wild-Type Oregon-R flies are orally exposed to sublethal concentrations of GBHs. Egg development was assessed by tracking the progress of eggs laid on

Ana Beatriz Rodrigues¹, Ilias Semmouri³, Albano Pinto^{1,2}, Inês P.E. Macário^{1,2}, Sérgio M. Marques^{1,2}, Joana Lourenço^{1,2}, Inês Domingues^{1,2}, **Joana Luísa Pereira**^{1,2}✉ jlpereira@ua.pt, Jana Asselman³

¹ Department of Biology, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

² CESAM – Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies, University of Aveiro, Portugal

³ Blue Growth Research Lab, Ghent University, Bluebridge Building, Ostend Science Park 1, 8400, Ostend, Belgium

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Background

Increasing anthropogenic activities are impacting aquatic ecosystems, leading to contamination events that pose potential deleterious effects to organisms [1]. Cadmium is a trace metal with no essential biological role known and particularly harmful due to its high toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulative properties [2].

Epigenetic and phenotypic responses that are responsive to Cd exposure can be integrated to understand the toxicity of the metal to copepods.

Aim

This study aims to understand the effects of short-term cadmium exposure on the copepod *Acartia tonsa*, a zooplanktonic marine species with important ecological role [3], integrating total **DNA methylation** changes with phenotypic changes concerning **DNA damage** and **oxidative stress** at the sub-individual level, as well as **behaviour** at the individual level.

Methods

1 Exposure

Evaluated endpoints	Exposure [Cd] µg/L	Replication
DNA	EC ₂₀ = 238.76	10 replicates 70 adults/replicate
Genotoxicity	EC ₂₀ = 238.76	5 replicates 30 adults/replicate
Oxidative Stress and Damage	EC ₂₀ = 238.76	4 replicates 80 adults/replicate
Behaviour	904.258, 324.64, 281.6963, 238.76 (EC ₂₀)	68 adult individuals per treatment

2 Biomarkers

Results

- Global 5-mC DNA methylation levels slightly decreased among exposed copepods, but not significantly compared to the control group.
- Results indicate a significant increase in GST activity and genotoxicity due to cadmium exposure (t-test, $p < 0.05$). Lipid peroxidation also increased, although this change was not statistically significant.
- Swimming behaviour was affected at cadmium concentrations higher than that eliciting changes in other biomarkers, though the effects were not statistically significant.

References

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Takeaway

- These findings highlight the sub-lethal effects of cadmium on *Acartia tonsa* and the convenience of multi-level biomarkers in assessing ecosystem health under human-induced stress.
- Despite limited knowledge on copepod epigenetics, evidence suggests epigenetic changes may aid rapid adaptation and phenotypic plasticity.
- This approach may clarify the links between epigenetic changes, gene expression, and phenotypic responses, helping to characterize the molecular basis of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) for cadmium-induced toxicity in *Acartia tonsa*.